

Galaxy Clusters Across Cosmic Time

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Galaxy Clusters Across Cosmic Time

4 days of talks and posters on
theory and observations of
clusters of galaxies

Galaxy evolution

Cluster evolution

Masses

Use as cosmological probes

Galaxy Clusters Across Cosmic Time

But, whether theory or observations, and whatever the spectral band, in this location we discussed the

Galaxy Clusters Across Cosmic Time

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“Aix-ray” properties of clusters

Opening Talk – Key Questions?

Andrea Biviano

- Many physical processes for changing galaxies. No one dominant process.
- Is there a universal (NFW) profile for clusters? Concentration-mass relation?
- Masses: easy methods (proxies) vs. hard methods?
- Cosmological probes: what will Euclid do for clusters?

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters

- Review – [Benedetta Vulcani](#)
 - Effect of environment strong in galaxy subtypes.
 - star forming fraction
 - gas content
 - morphologies
 - Jellyfish galaxies – lots of nice new data

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- LoCuSS: Pre-processing in galaxy groups falling in to massive galaxy clusters at $z=0.2$ - **Matteo Bianconi**
 - Groups have lower star formation fractions and a flatter trend with distance than clusters.
- The SAMI Galaxy Survey: The impact of the cluster environment on the star formation of infalling galaxies - **Matt Owers**
 - SAMI: new IF survey of large sample of galaxies, 8 targeted clusters.
 - 11% of non-passive cluster galaxies have young stars but no current star formation

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- Environmental Effects and Star Formation Quenching in SpARCS 0.1 - **Irene Pintos-Castro**
 - Drop in star-forming fraction to center is larger and begins further out at low z than high z
- Studying the population of galaxies in X-ray groups and clusters with the XXL survey - **Valentina Guglielmo**
 - Supercluster region with 14 groups/clusters
 - High mass galaxies not affected by environment. Others effected only in cluster cores.

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- Were the most compact and most diffuse stellar systems in galaxy clusters both formed by stripping?
 - **Carolin Wittmann**
 - Faint, low surface brightness, ultra-diffuse galaxies in core of Perseus.
 - No evidence of disruption, but lack of higher mass --- due to cluster tides?

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- Stellar-to-halo mass relation of cluster galaxies: **Anna Niemiec**
 - Stellar/halo mass of galaxies vs. location in clusters.
 - Dark matter tidal stripping.
- Analysis of galaxies' colour components in the Hubble frontier fields clusters - **Rémy Joseph**
 - Use new technique to separate background lensed and cluster galaxies to decompose galaxies into color components.

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- Optical properties of XXL clusters - **Marina Ricci**
 - Method to avoid bias from photometric redshifts.
 - M^* gets brighter at higher redshift, but faint end slope doesn't change.
- Evidence for dry merger driven BCG growth in XXL-100-GC X-ray clusters - **Jon Willis**
 - Does BCG growth switch from star forming mergers ($z > 1$) to dry mergers ($z < 1$)?
 - Mass BCG proportional to M_{cluster} at low z .

Galaxy Evolution In Clusters (Cont.)

- The special growth history of brightest cluster galaxies: **Carlo Nipoti**
 - Effect of cannibalism on structure of BCG.
 - Orbits not circularized. Higher mass ratio mergers, more tangential orbits.
- An ALMA Study of Gas-Rich Galaxies in $z \sim 1.6$ Galaxy Clusters: **Allison Noble**
 - Hint of wonderful results to come from ALMA
 - Cluster galaxies have higher gas fraction than field at high z ?
 - Large variation between clusters

What is a Galaxy Cluster? From the BCG to Beyond the Virial Radius

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Review of ICM - Dominique Eckert

- Global properties of ICM have tight scaling relations when central regions removed
- Role of merger and accretion shocks
- Connection of shocks with radio relics
- Can we detect accretion shocks?
- New evidence that radio halo clusters have strong turbulence

What is a Galaxy Cluster? From the BCG to Beyond the Virial Radius

Invited – SZ vs. X-ray Cluster Selection: Fabio Gastaldello

- SZ selected clusters more disturbed than X-ray selected
- Due mainly to cool-core bias in X-rays
- Some effect of X-ray underluminous clusters?

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Probing galaxy interaction mechanisms in merging clusters with HI: **Tom Scott**
 - Disturbed HI more common in clusters
- Ram Pressure Stripping in Coma: **Michael Gregg**
 - Beautiful HST images
 - “Pillars” of stripped gas/dust with star formation, ionization front, half S0/Sb galaxies, jellyfish galaxies

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Exploring the outskirts of galaxy clusters with Planck: **Herve Bourdin**
 - ICM dust
 - ICM filaments and inhomogeneities
- LoCuSS: An XMM survey of X-ray groups being accreted by massive clusters: **Chris Haines**
 - Excess of $\sim 10^{14}$ Msun groups
 - About 50% of cluster mass comes from accreting groups

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Surprising existence of massive and large molecular gas reservoirs in a distant protocluster:

Helmut Dannerbauer

- Spider Web Galaxy in protocluster at $z=2.16$
- Within large reservoir of molecular gas
- BCG formation by star formation rather than mergers

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Review: Lensing and Multiwavelength Observations -
Mathilde Jauzac
 - A2744 – many cores, messy mergers
 - Not impossibly rare in simulations, but require careful analysis
 - New MUSE AO system
 - New BUFFALO survey on HST

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

Invited: Evolution of Chemical Composition over Cosmic Time - [Aurora Simionescu](#)

- How are metals made?
 - CC vs. SNIa for making heavy elements
 - SN Ia happen later? Maybe not, delays ~ 1 Gyr
 - $\alpha/\text{Fe} \sim$ constant with radius beyond BCG
 - No evolution with redshift at present

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Thermodynamical properties of the ICM: present and future constraints from ATHENA: **Stefano Ettori**
 - ATHENA = >10x present instruments
 - Chemical evolution of lots of elements to high redshift and radius
 - X-COP project. X-ray and SZ to large radii
 - T, n, P, K vs. radius
- Exploring the fossil record of cluster assembly: the intra-cluster light: **Mireia Montes**
 - Abundance gradient in ICL
 - Ages 2-6 Gyr less than BCG --- later assembly

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- Ten Billion Years of Brightest Cluster Galaxy Alignments: **Michael West**
 - BCGs align with clusters which align with filaments
 - Test at high z --- BCGs still aligned to $z \sim 2$
- Fossil galaxy systems: observed and simulated properties: **Aisha Kundert**
 - Satellite galaxy distributions show substructure
 - Fossil centrals have more major mergers, after $z \sim 1$ (Illustris simulations)

What is a Galaxy Cluster? (Cont.)

- EasyCritics II: catalog of strongly-lensing galaxy groups and clusters in CHFTLenS – **Mauricio Carrasco**
 - Automatic method to pick out strong lenses

How and How Well Do We Measure Masses?

The food in Provence was good

How and How Well Do We Measure Masses?

- Review: Multi-Probe Approach - **Mauro Sereno**
 - X-ray vs. SZ vs. Lensing vs. Dynamics
 - Strategies for combining different techniques and simulations
- Invited: Cosmological Constraint from shear peaks - **Nicolas Martinet**
 - Map LSS via shear, test cosmology
 - KIDS = Kilo Degree Survey

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- Using XMM and Chandra to probe the mass distribution in the most distant massive galaxy clusters - **Jacopo Bartalucci**
 - Concentration lower, gas fraction higher at high z ?
 - Some tension with WL
- AMICO: detection of galaxy clusters in the Euclid survey - **Matteo Maturi**
 - Multi-band optimal matched filters
 - Will be applied to Euclid when launched

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- HeCS-red: A Hectospec Survey of red-sequence selected clusters - **Ken Rines**
 - redMaPPer: red sequence selected clusters
 - Mass-richness correlation, with outliers
- A combined analysis of strong lensing and dynamics in galaxy clusters - **Tomás Verdugo**
 - Better constraints

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- Combined analysis of galaxy clusters: triaxiality and mass components - **Mario Bonamigo**
 - Triaxiality can resolve disagreements of mass probes, remove orientation bias
 - Separation of mass components (gas, galaxies, DM)

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- Review: Hydrostatic Mass Bias in Simulations - **Elena Rasia**
 - ~10% mass bias in simulations, correlated with major mergers
 - Temperature bias due to inhomogeneities in X-ray and SZ
- Invited: Measuring Masses with SZ - **Rémi Adam**
 - High spatial resolution SZ images of clusters with ALMA, NIKA(2), and MUSTANG(2)
 - Combine X-ray and SZ images to give $T(r)$, $P(r)$ --- mass profiles

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- The AMALGAM project. Weak lensing masses and mass profiles for 120 massive clusters. - **Raphael Gavazzi**
 - Use SExtractor to get shapes of bg galaxies
 - Probabilistic photo-z's
- Calibrating the Planck cluster mass scale with cluster velocity dispersions - **Stefania Amodeo**
 - Planck mass bias could reconcile Planck and X-ray cosmology

Measure Masses (Cont.)

- New dynamical analysis for the strong lensing cluster Abell 1703 - **Karina Rojas**
 - No evidence for substructure
 - Unusual lensing ring
- A hierarchical study of galaxy clusters - **Maggie Lieu**
 - Hierarchical inference method to stack WL observations of low mass clusters

How and How Well Do We Use Them As Cosmological Probes?

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- Review – SZ Cluster Surveys - **Nabila Aghanim**
 - SZ survey revolution, particularly with Planck
 - ~2600 clusters, $z(\text{med}) \sim 0.3$, $M(\text{med}) \sim 4 \times 10^{14} \text{ Msun}$
 - Confirm T_{CMB} proportional to $(1 + z)$
 - Cosmology from cluster counts, test for Dark Energy
 - Test for Ω_m and σ_8 . Tension with X-ray, other SZ
 - Reanalysis with Planck τ , reduces tension?

How and How Well Do We Use Them As Cosmological Probes?

- Invited – X-ray Clusters, eeHIFLUGCS – eROSITA – Athena - **Thomas Reiprich**
 - Evidence for anisotropy in Universe?
 - eeHIFLUGCS: more, fainter clusters, extends to groups
 - eROSITA update
 - Good limits on Ω_m , σ_8 , w , w_a , neutrino masses
 - Athena: groups at high z

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Optical follow-up of galaxy cluster candidates detected by Planck satellite in the PSZ2 catalogue - **Alejandro Aguado**
 - Do Planck clusters in order of decreasing SNR
 - ~400 clusters, ~150 new clusters
- Dark Matter Composition from Gravitational Lensing of Individual Stars - **Nick Kaiser**
 - Transient Icarus in MACS J1149
 - Blue supergiant star being imaged
 - Smooth cluster plus point mass

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Dust in Galaxy Clusters: Modeling at Millimeter Wavelengths and Impact on Planck Cluster Cosmology - **Jean-Baptiste Melin**
 - Reconcile SZ and CMB cosmology? No
 - Will affect CMB-S4 experiments
- HICOSMO -- X-ray analysis of a complete sample of galaxy clusters - **Gerritt Schellenberger**
 - HIFLUGCS sample, hydrostatic masses
 - Cosmological parameters $\Omega_m = 0.3$, $\sigma_8 = 0.9$

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Cosmology with XMM serendipitous clusters using a forward modelling method - **Jethro Ridd**
 - X-CLASS serendipitous survey 265 clusters, optical follow-up for a portion for photo-z's

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Review: Cosmology with Cluster - **Florian Pacaud**
 - Measurements of mass function of clusters and proxies
 - ROSAT, XXL XMM surveys
 - Spatial distribution of clusters --- power spectrum
 - Baryon fraction gives distance, geometry

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Invited: Euclid Clusters as probes of cosmology and LSS --- **Gabriela Sartoris**
 - Euclid catalog of clusters
 - Results from single massive clusters at high redshift
 - Power-spectrum, including z distribution
 - Tests of more exotic physics

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Systematic errors in strong lensing models of galaxy clusters: Implications for cosmography in FF-simulated clusters - **Ana Acebron**
 - Frontier Fields clusters vs. Mock clusters to determine systematic errors
- Future of galaxy clusters - **Mel Ulmer**
 - The Universe in 10 billion years or cluster astrophysics in 10 years?
 - LUVOIR 9.5 m telescope
 - Adaptive optics using magneto-restriction

Cosmological Probes? (Cont.)

- Constraining Cosmological Parameters with the Velocity Distribution Function and HeCS-SZ Clusters
 - Michelle Ntampaka
 - New method to go directly from measured galaxy velocities to cosmology

Many Excellent Posters

eROSITA - Covariances of galaxy cluster parameters and their impact on cosmology

Käfer Florian

The Abell 1763 Supercluster: A star forming filament, perturbing substructure and a remnant cool core

Louise Edwards

A New X-Ray Selected Galaxy Cluster Sample from the ROSAT All-Sky Survey

Xu Weiwei

A weak lensing analysis of the three most relaxed distant galaxy clusters from the 2500 deg² SPT-SZ Survey

Beatriz Hernandez,

The Pressure Profile Shape and the Dynamical States of Galaxy Clusters

Ana Mikler

Posters

Jens Eler: Planck's view of the spectrum of the SZ effect

Leyla Ebrahimpour : mass estimation of galaxy clusters using gaussian processes

GUPTA ANSHU: survival of the fittest: the impact of ram pressure stripping on star forming galaxies

LASSAILLE FREDERIC : An alternative to dark matter: SMT

FERRAGAMO ANTONIO: velocity dispersion: biased or not biased ?

BONJEAN VICTOR : Gas and galaxies in inter-cluster filaments

NAGARAJAN AARTI: weak lensing mass calibration of the SZ effect using APEX SZ galaxy clusters

SEMCZUK Marcin : spiral arms in galaxies orbiting a virgo like cluster

GOUIN CELINE: multipolar moments of weak lensing signal around clusters

TAM SUTIENG: large scale filament detection with gravitational lensing

Posters

RAIHAN FATIMAH : testing the accuracy of 3D HST photometric redshifts for weak lensing studies

WIK Daniel : heating and acceleration at galaxy cluster shocks : insights from nustar

MAHADEV PANDGE: discovery of mlc-scale xray tail in MACS 0553

Juan Magana : strong lensing modeling of galaxy clusters to test cosmography

BAGCHI JOYDEEP : saraswati : an extremely massive 200 megaparsec scale supercluster

LOPEZ PAULO: the environmental dependence of AGNs in clusters and field

LEMAUX BRIAN: on the proper selection of post starburst galaxies
ORELSE

STREBLYANSKA ALINA: presence of strong lensing effects in the Planck discovered clusters

Posters

SARRON FLORIAN: galaxy clusters GLFS in the CFHTLS

GREGG MICHAEL (who finally gave a talk, after Randall's cancellation) : virgo intergalactic globulars

INESON JUDITH : jet environments and energetics, and prospects for finding galaxy groups with new radio surveys

VAN ENGELEN ALEXANDER: galaxy clusters from CMB-S4, the polarised SZ effect, and reionisation

DURET FLORENCE : evolution of cluster galaxies based on the faint end of their galaxy luminosity function

Kiyun Yun : quantifying the spatial and time scales for star formation, stripping, and quenching of satellite galaxies with illustrious TNG

Konstantinos migkas : anisotropy of the galaxy cluster Xray luminosity temperature relation

THORSTEN Lisker : how can we decide which galaxy properties were set at birth and which by environmental transformation ?

Posters

Josefina Michea : the evolution of the galaxy cluster red sequence at intermediate redshift

Christoph Engler : properties of Illustrious galaxies in observer's phase space

Linda urich : young, metal-enriched cores in early type dwarf galaxies in Virgo

Carolina parroni : the weak lensing analysis of the CFHTLS and NGVS RedGOLD galaxy clusters

Perez Garcia : multiwavelength cross match in galaxy clusters

Nick Henden : exploring AGN feedback models in cosmological simulations

Monday – Opening the Bottle!

The Bar is Closing – Drink Up!

Thanks to the Organizers!!

(Particularly Marceau!)

This was an **Aix-cellent** meeting in a wonderful place!

